

SWACHH BHARAT ABHIYAN – INDIA’S VISION TO FUTURE

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Abstract

India is a prosperous country. The prosperity of India is depends on different areas . when we consider the nation as a prosperous nation we always keep some points in mind. While describing prosperity of India we have to consider some nodal points of prosperity.India is an ancient civilization. It is considered to be a pious nation, its peoples are very religious and they follow their faith very devotedly, but it is a sad reality that all the cleanliness and piousness is only confined to religious activities.Dr. A.P.J.Kalam had a vision of India 2020. He prepared a plan for this and he described the plan as transforming the India as a nation into a developed country as developed india. In this plan there are many areas of the progress of the nation. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is one of the important area for the rapid progress and ultimately the prosperity of the India.

Present paper focuses on how the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan play a vital role in India’s vision for the transformation of the developing India into a developed Indiaand a clean,green and rich India.

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NODAL POINTS OF INDIAN PROSPERITY

1. **PEACE, SECURITY & NATIONAL UNITY** – Physical security both from external and internal threats—strong national defence, domestic law enforcement and social harmony.
2. **FOOD & NUTRITIONAL SECURITY** – A vibrant, highly productive commercial farm sector that can ensure food & nutritional security, generate employment opportunities, stimulate industrialisation, and produce renewable energy from biomass and fuel crops.
3. **JOBS FOR ALL** – A constitutional commitment to ensure the right of all citizens to a sustainable livelihood that will provide them with the purchasing power needed to freely cast their economic

votes in the market place.

4. **KNOWLEDGE** – 100 per cent literacy & school education, and vocational training for all new entrants to the workforce, to equip youth with the knowledge and skills needed to thrive in an increasingly competitive world: adult education programmes to compensate working age school drop-outs for the lack of education, and continued investment in science and technology to improve productivity, quality of life and the environment.
5. **HEALTH** – Expansion of the infrastructure for public health and medical care to ensure health for all.
6. **TECHNOLOGY & INFRASTRUCTURE** – Continuous expansion of the physical infrastructure for rapid low-cost transportation and communication that is required for rapid economic growth and international competitiveness. Application of computers to improve access to knowledge and information, and increase in the speed, efficiency and convenience of activities in all fields of life.
7. **GLOBALISATION** – Successful integration of India with world economy.
8. **GOOD GOVERNANCE** – Farsighted and dynamic leadership to maximise national prosperity, individual freedom and social equity through responsive, transparent and accountable administration that removes all the bottlenecks to economic development.
9. **WORK VALUES** - Activation of all these nodal points requires firm and determined adherence to high values, including prompt decision-making, disciplined execution, systematic implementation, finely tuned co-ordination, unceasing effort and endurance. Along with this in India seems to be making rapid progress in every field. The ten areas that will make all the difference are

Roads

- 1) Railways
- 2) Electricity
- 3) Oil
- 4) Subsidies
- 5) Swachh Bharat Abhiyan
- 6) Bureaucracy
- 7) Foreign policy and economy
- 8) Startups

While describing prosperity of India we have to consider some nodal points of prosperity. India is an ancient civilization. It is considered to be a pious nation, its peoples are very religious and they follow their faith very devotedly, but it is a sad reality that all the cleanliness and piety is only

confined to religious activities. Dr. A.P.J. Kalam had a vision of India 2020. He prepared a plan for this and he described the plan as transforming the India as a nation into a developed country as developed India. In this plan there are many areas of the progress of the nation. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is one of the important areas for the rapid progress and ultimately the prosperity of the India.

Present paper focuses on how the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan plays a vital role in India's vision for the transformation of the developing India into a developed India and a clean, green and rich India.

India vision 2020 was initially a document prepared by the technology information, forecasting and assessment council of India's Department of Science and Technology under the chairmanship of A.P.J. Abdul Kalam and a team of 500 experts.

According to Kalam the plan follows- "transforming the nation into a developed country. Five areas in combination have been identified based on India's core competence, natural resources and talented manpower or integrated action to double the growth rate of GDP & realize the vision of developed India."

Differences are as Mahatma Gandhi has rightly said "sanitation is more important than independence" he was aware of the pathetic situation and Indian rural people at the time and he dreamt of a clean India when he emphasizes on cleanliness and sanitation as an integral part of living. Unfortunately we have completed 70 years of independence and we have only about 30% of the rural households with access to toilets.

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is an important area for the developing India. Food, shelter, clothing and education are the basic needs of every human being but now in the changing scenario of India the new needs arise i.e. health of the human being cleanliness at all levels as India has been known as a country with serious public cleanliness problems. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has also been known by Swachh Bharat Mission is a nation wide campaign in India for the period of 2014 to 2019 that aims to clean up the cities, towns & rural areas.

The objectives of the Swachh Bharat Mission include-

- To improve quality of life of people living in the rural areas. Motivate people to maintain sanitation in rural areas to complete the vision of Swachh Bharat by 2019.
- To motivate local working bodies as community panchayat.
- To make available the required sustainable sanitation facilities.
- To develop advanced environmental sanitation systems manageable by the community especially to focus on solid and liquid waste management in the rural areas.
- To achieve an "open defecation free" India by 2 Oct 2019, the 150th anniversary of the birth of

mahatma Gandhi by constructing 90 million toilets in rural India. The mission has also contribute to India reaching sustainable developed goal.

- To bring about an improvement in the general quality of life in the rural areas by promoting cleanliness, hygiene and eliminating open defecation.

Need of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan

Swachh Bharat Mission is very necessary to run continuously in India until it gets its goal. It is very essential for the people in India to really get the feeling of physical, mental, social and intellectual well being. It is to advance the living status in India in real means which can be started by bringing all over cleanliness. India is the second most populated country in the world. Cleanliness is one of the major needs to become a fully developed country.

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is a politics free campaign inspired by patriotism it is launched as a responsibility of each and every Indian citizen to make this country a swachh country. This campaign has initiated people globally towards cleanliness. Teachers and students of schools are joining this 'clean India campaign' very actively with great fervour and joy. It is a nationwide clean lines campaign implemented to fulfill the vision and mission of clean India one day. As Mahatma Gandhi as he always dreamed and was keen to make this country a clean country. He had tried for clean India. during his time by motivating people through his campaigns and slogans however it was only partially successful because of the limited involvement of the people of India.

But after so many years swachh Bharat Mission was again started by the Govt. of India to make dream of clean India come true till 150th birth anniversary the Mahatma Gandhi. It is a big challenge for all the citizen a India. It is only possible if each and every person living in India would understand this campaign, their own responsibility and try to join hands together to make it a successful mission. The mission is promoted by the many famous Indian personalities to spread the mission as an awareness programme throughout the country. The aim of the mission to clear all the rural and urban areas in order to present this country as an ideal country before the world. The mission has targeted aims eliminating the open defecation, converting insanitary toilets into pour flush toilets, eradicating manual scavenging, complete disposal and reuse of solid and liquid wastes.

By the end when we think about the accomplishment of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan in developing India it definitely shows the participation and involvement of people in this campaign was definitely huge and also started showing positive result in recent time, but the most important thing is the continuation of this process. Let us pledge together that we will continue doing our bit in making our surrounding and environment clean and green and make our country respected in the world community.

In Conclusion we can say that the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan aims at bringing behavioural changes in people to motivate health practices ,spreading cleanliness awareness among the people and strengthening the cleanliness, system in all areas. It helps in creating user friendly environment for all the private sectors interested for investing in India for cleanliness maintenance . The effect of the missions has already started showing its results in almost all the parts with the active involvement of people from all the walks of life . If the same pace continues in making the country clean and green then the dream of Mahatma Gandhi will definitely come true on his 150th birth anniversary In 2019 and that will be the great achievement for all Indians..

The government came out with a cleanliness ranking for a cities and towns and is looking at multiple ways to clean up our public places. But more importantly, when a government targets building millions of toilets with a vengeance to put an end to the endemic problem of defecating in public, when things begin to look optimistic ; maybe, just maybe , we can finally dream of a going from a developing India to a developed India.

When we think about Indias vision 2020 we have to remember these golden days of Indian prosperity. As like A.P.J.Kalam the great poet, writer and philosopher and the Nobel Laureate Rabindranath Tagore's had his Vision of India.

The vision articulated by Rabindranath Tagore is all encompassing in every sense. It has laid down what he considered to be the basic constituents of the "heaven of freedom". We can identify eight components of this vision reflected in the poem quoted earlier, which we can attempt to translate into operational terms for India's vision 2020.

Where the mind is without fear – Peace and security, internal as well as external, is the first and most essential foundation for the nation's future progress. Fearlessness can only be attained when this security extends to cover, over and above our physical safety, our social rights and economic well being, to eliminate all forms of vulnerability and discrimination.

Where the head is held high – Self-respect and self-esteem are the psychological foundations for the development of individuality and individual initiative, which are the means through which the nation builds its strength and fulfils its aspirations. The nation prospers through the development and flowering of all its citizens as individuals. Health, education and employment opportunities for all, and awareness of our rich spiritual and cultural heritage are the essential bases for fostering self-respect and self-esteem.

Where knowledge is free – Development takes place when people become aware of opportunities for advancement and acquire the knowledge needed to convert those opportunities into practical accomplishments. Knowledge in the form of education, technology and access to a wide range of

information is a catalyst for individual and social progress. The free flow of knowledge is the basis for a free and prosperous society.

Where the world has not been broken up into fragments by narrow domestic walls – The spirit of globalisation which is rapidly reshaping the world today cannot be better expressed. The accelerated flow and exchange of trade, capital, technology, information and people will create unprecedented opportunities for the progress and prosperity of all countries that can transcend the narrow confines of national boundaries. India can however realise its full potential in the wider world only when it is internally united, surmounting all the centrifugal forces that overlook our common heritage and accentuate our differences.

Where words come out from the depth of truth — Integrity, honesty and trustworthiness are the essential foundations for a successful democracy and a prosperous society. Both good governance and commercial success demand rigorous standards of transparency, accountability and reliability in word and action.

Where tireless striving stretches its arms towards perfection – Prosperity is the result of productivity and efficiency which require the highest level of productive skills, technological excellence and human effort.

These threads from Rabindranath's poem are the vital strands from which a fulfilling vision of India 2020 can be woven.

Where the mind is without fear and the head is held high.

Where knowledge is free.

Where the world has not been broken up into fragments

By narrow domestic walls.

Where words come out from the depth of truth.

Where tireless striving stretches its arms towards perfection.

Where the clear stream of reason has not lost its way

Into the dreary desert sand of dead habit.

Where the mind is led forward by Thee

Into ever-widening thought and action.

Into that heaven of freedom, my Father, let my country

A Clean India is a green India

A green India is a rich India AND It will provide better world for next generation.

Need of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan

Swachh Bharat mission is very necessary to run continuously in India until it gets its goal. It is very essential for the people in India to really get the feeling of physical, mental, social and intellectual well being. It is to advance the living status in India in real means which can be started by bringing all over cleanliness. Below I have mentioned some points proving the urgent need of 'Swachh Bharat Abhiyan' in India:

- It is really very essential to eliminate the open defecation in India as well as making toilets facility available to everyone.
- It is needed in India to convert the insanitary toilets into flushing toilets.
- It is necessary in order to eradicate the manual scavenging system.
- It is to implement the proper waste management through the scientific processes, hygienic disposal, reuse, and recycling of the municipal solid wastes.
- It is to bring behavioral changes among Indian people regarding maintenance of personal hygiene and practice of healthy sanitation methods.
- It is to create global awareness among common masses living in rural areas and link it to the public health.
- It is to support working bodies to design, execute and operate the waste disposal systems locally.
- It is to bring private-sector participation to develop sanitary facilities throughout India.
- It is to make India a clean and green India.
- It is necessary to improve the quality of life of people in rural areas.
- It is to bring sustainable sanitation practices by motivating communities and Panchayati Raj Institutions through the awareness programmes like health education.
- It is to bring the dream of Bapu to come true.